

Alignment of ILOs–TLAs–ATs for the course MG2040 Assembly Technology at KTH Royal Institute of Technology

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Integrating Sustainability into Assembly Technology Education: A Course Redesign Approach Based on Constructive Alignment

Table 2. Re-aligned ILOs: Mapping sustainability dimensions and knowledge for the course MG2040 Assembly Technology.

ID	Old ILO (current course)	New ILO (in- tegrated sustaina- bility)	Sus- tainability Dimen- sion(s)	Specific Sustainability Knowledge Addressed
ILO1	Correctly position the assembly process within the manufacturing domain	Explain the role of assembly in manufacturing systems including environmental, economic, and human-	Envi- ronmental, Economic, Social, Hu- man-cen- tered	Understanding assembly as a system-level leverage point influencing: resource consumption (materials, energy), lifecycle cost, supply chain structure, and worker conditions. Introduces systems thinking and the role of assembly in circular

		centered sustainability impacts		economy and sustainability integration
ILO2	Produce mathematical and feature models of assemblies	Develop and use assembly models integrating technical and sustainability KPIs (e.g., cost, energy, ergonomics)	Environmental, Economic, Human-centered	Ability to integrate multi-dimensional KPIs into models: energy consumption, carbon footprint, lifecycle cost, ergonomic load. Supports quantification of sustainability performance and decision-making based on integrated indicators
ILO3	Account for dynamic and static constraints of assembly processes	Analyze technical, environmental, and human constraints in manual and automated assembly systems	Environmental, Human-centered, Economic	Identification of constraints beyond technical : energy limits, emissions, ergonomic stress, cognitive load, safety. Introduces trade-offs between system performance and sustainability constraints
ILO4	Analyze product and define feasible assembly sequences	Evaluate assembly sequences considering efficiency, sustainability (e.g., disassembly), and human factors	Environmental, Human-centered, Economic	Knowledge of design for disassembly , sequence impact on material recovery , and ergonomic implications. Understanding how sequencing affects lifecycle sustainability and operator workload
ILO5	Describe the function of assembly system elements	Explain assembly system elements including their impact on sustainability (automation, resource use, human role)	Environmental, Human-centered, Economic, Social	Understanding how system elements (robots, tools, operators) influence energy use, resource efficiency, human roles, and job quality . Includes human-automation interaction and implications for workforce
ILO6	Evaluate impact of product design using DFA	Apply DFA and Design for Sustainability (DFS), including design for disassembly and material efficiency	Environmental, Economic	Knowledge of material minimization, design for disassembly , modularity, and lifecycle impact. Extension of DFA to include circularity and environmental performance
ILO7	Discuss trade-offs between assembly and manufacturing	Evaluate trade-offs between cost, performance, sustainability, and human factors	Economic, Environmental, Human-centered, Social	Ability to perform multi-criteria decision-making considering lifecycle cost, environmental impact, ergonomics, and social implications. Understanding conflicting objectives and compromise solutions
ILO8	Identify requirements	Design assembly workstations	Human-centered,	Knowledge of ergonomic design , safety, cognitive load, and

	for assembly station design	considering ergonomics, safety, and resource efficiency	Environmental	energy/resource-efficient workstation design. Focus on worker well-being and sustainable operations
ILO9	Calculate costs and KPIs of assembly systems	Evaluate assembly systems using economic, environmental, and social KPIs	Economic, Environmental, Social, Human-centered	Ability to define and apply multi-dimensional KPIs: lifecycle cost, energy consumption, emissions, safety, ergonomics, job quality. Supports holistic system evaluation and sustainability reporting

Table 1. TLAs for ILOs 1 to 9.

ID	Teaching Activities (Teacher)	Learning Activities (Students)	Alignment Comment
TLA1.1	Deliver lecture on assembly as a system integrator within manufacturing	Take notes and ask clarification questions	Establishes structured conceptual understanding and supports Time on Task (5) and High Expectations (6)
TLA1.2	Present industrial case studies highlighting sustainability trade-offs	Analyze cases collaboratively in groups	Promotes Active Learning (3) and Cooperation Among Students (2) through real-world problem analysis
TLA1.3	Facilitate guided class discussions	Engage in discussion and critical reflection	Enhances Student-Faculty Contact (1) and Respect for Diverse Ways of Learning (7)
TLA2.1	Demonstrate modeling techniques and KPI integration	Practice modeling through guided exercises	Supports Active Learning (3) and Time on Task (5) through hands-on engagement
TLA2.2	Provide simulation-based examples	Apply models to predefined scenarios	Reinforces Active Learning (3)
TLA2.3	Facilitate hands-on workshops	Collaboratively develop assembly models	Promotes Cooperation Among Students (2) and Prompt Feedback (4)
TLA3.1	Deliver lecture on assembly constraints	Identify and classify constraints	Supports Time on Task (5)
TLA3.2	Present case-based examples	Analyze constraints within real scenarios	Promotes Active Learning (3)
TLA3.3	Facilitate group workshops	Perform collaborative constraint analysis	Encourages Cooperation Among Students (2) and Active Learning (3)

TLA4.1	Teach assembly sequencing methods	Apply sequencing techniques	Supports Active Learning (3) and Time on Task (5)
TLA4.2	Provide alternative scenarios	Compare sequencing alternatives	Promotes Active Learning (3)
TLA4.3	Guide evaluation exercises	Justify selected sequences	Reinforces High Expectations (6)
TLA5.1	Deliver lecture with demonstrations	Observe and interpret system components	Supports Respect for Diverse Ways of Learning (7)
TLA5.2	Provide multimedia examples	Analyze system configurations	Promotes Active Learning (3)
TLA5.3	Facilitate discussions	Compare alternative system designs	Encourages Student–Faculty Contact (1)
TLA6.1	Teach DFA and DFS methodologies	Apply methods to exercises	Supports Active Learning (3)
TLA6.2	Provide redesign examples	Redesign product systems	Promotes Active Learning (3) and creativity
TLA6.3	Facilitate group work	Evaluate alternative designs	Supports Cooperation Among Students (2)
TLA7.1	Present decision scenarios	Analyze trade-offs	Supports Active Learning (3)
TLA7.2	Facilitate structured debates	Argue different perspectives	Promotes Student–Faculty Contact (1) and Respect for Diverse Ways of Learning (7)
TLA7.3	Introduce decision frameworks	Apply multi-criteria tools	Reinforces Time on Task (5)
TLA8.1	Demonstrate design tools	Design workstation layouts	Supports Active Learning (3)
TLA8.2	Introduce ergonomic methods	Evaluate ergonomic conditions	Promotes Active Learning (3)
TLA8.3	Facilitate iterative sessions	Refine and improve designs	Supports Prompt Feedback (4)
TLA9.1	Teach KPI frameworks	Calculate performance indicators	Supports Time on Task (5)
TLA9.2	Provide real-world examples	Interpret KPI results	Promotes Active Learning (3)
TLA9.3	Guide exercises	Build KPI dashboards	Supports Active Learning (3)

Table 2. ATs for ILOs 1 to 9.

ID	Assessment Task	Description	Grading Criteria	Learning Preferences Alignment
AT1.1	Written exam	Analyze the role of assembly including sustainability dimensions	Accuracy, integration of sustainability aspects, clarity of argumentation	Supports Felder–Silverman (analytical, sequential) and VARK (read/write) learners
AT1.2	Reflection assignment	Reflect on the role of assembly in a real-world system	Depth of reflection, linkage to theory, clarity of expression	Supports Kolb (reflective observation) and VARK (read/write, verbal) learners
AT2.1	Project modeling task	Develop an assembly model including sustainability KPIs	Correctness, completeness, integration of KPIs	Supports Kolb (active experimentation) and Felder–Silverman (global, active) learners
AT2.2	Practical assignment	Apply modeling approach to a new scenario	Application capability, accuracy, interpretation quality	Supports Felder–Silverman (sequential) and VARK (kinesthetic) learners
AT3.1	Project analysis	Identify and evaluate system constraints	Completeness, depth, relevance	Supports Kolb (concrete experience + reflection) and Felder–Silverman (global)
AT3.2	Exam question	Analyze constraints in a given scenario	Accuracy, reasoning, clarity	Supports Felder–Silverman (analytical, sequential)
AT4.1	Project comparison	Evaluate and compare alternative sequences	Justification, criteria use, clarity	Supports Felder–Silverman (analytical + global)
AT4.2	Oral presentation	Present and justify chosen solution	Argumentation, clarity, engagement	Supports VARK (aural/verbal) and Kolb (active experimentation)
AT5.1	Exam	Describe assembly system elements	Accuracy, completeness	Supports VARK (read/write) and Felder–Silverman (sequential)
AT5.2	Project section	Analyze a real assembly system	Depth, application, clarity	Supports Kolb (concrete experience) and global learners
AT6.1	Project redesign	Apply DFA and DFS principles	Innovation, correctness, justification	Supports Kolb (active experimentation) and creative/global learners
AT6.2	Exam problem	Evaluate design alternatives	Analytical reasoning, accuracy	Supports Felder–Silverman (analytical)

AT7.1	Case-based exam	Evaluate trade-offs in context	Depth, balance, justification	Supports Felder–Silverman (analytical) and contextual learners
AT7.2	Project decision section	Justify design decisions	Argumentation, integration, clarity	Supports Kolb (reflective + active) and global learners
AT8.1	Project design	Develop workstation design	Functionality, ergonomics, feasibility	Supports Kolb (active experimentation) and VARK (kinesthetic)
AT8.2	Practical task	Perform ergonomic evaluation	Accuracy, application, clarity	Supports kinesthetic learners and applied learning
AT9.1	Project KPI analysis	Evaluate system performance	Completeness, interpretation, integration	Supports Kolb (integration) and Felder–Silverman (global)
AT9.2	Exam calculation	Compute KPIs	Accuracy, method, clarity	Supports analytical and sequential learners